

Short Communication

Silver Lining: Wound Care with Nanoparticle-impregnated Silk Sutures

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Received: 17 May 2024

Accepted: 26 September 2024

Published online: 31 January 2025

Keywords: : full thickness skin defects, decellularized ficus benjamina leaves scaffold, wound regeneration

The most widely used surgical equipment is suture material. Used appropriately, when indicated, it aids hemostasis and wound healing. However, it allows the formation of biofilm and changes the microenvironment of the surgical site resulting in surgical site infection (SSI). SSIs can lead to wound gaping and delayed wound healing resulting in longer hospitalizations. Research and developments in material science have brought antibiotic-coated sutures to markets. Silver is also known to possess anti-microbial and anti-bacterial properties. In this paper we present the process and evaluate the properties of silk sutures impregnated with silver nanoparticles. The silver nanoparticle impregnated sutures were superior to conventional sutures and could be produced inexpensively.

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Introduction

Surgical sutures represent the majority share (57%) of the worldwide surgical equipment's market due to their extensive use as surgical implants. They consist of biocompatible materials, either natural or synthetic fibres, and are categorized into multifilament, monofilament, braided, and twisted types [1].

Suture materials, due to their inherent fibre properties hold microbial flora onto them, resulting in biofilm formation followed by microbial colonization. This may initiate microbial infection, which if not treated on time, by removing the suture, can cause delayed healing and wound gaping [2]. The recovery from post-operative wound infections is a complex process with potential for further complications. Surgical site infections (SSI), which are linked to significant rates of mortality and morbidity, typically occur around the incision site [3]. To reduce the likelihood of wound infections, recent research has concentrated on developing sutures coated with antibiotics. These antibiotic-coated sutures have shown effective antibacterial properties in laboratory tests, animal experiments and clinical studies [4]. However, prolonged antibiotic use is recognized to promote bacterial resistance and enhance organism virulence. To mitigate antimicrobial resistance, researchers are currently directing their efforts toward developing novel antimicrobial agents.

In recent years, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) have garnered significant attention as the most extensively studied metallic nanoparticles. Numerous studies have documented the broad-spectrum antibacterial properties of AgNPs [5]. Several products incorporating silver nanoparticles are currently on the market, including biomedical devices, wound dressings, contraceptive devices, surgical instruments, and bone prostheses. It has emerged as a promising antimicrobial agent to combat multidrug-resistant microorganisms. Environmentally-friendly nano-synthetic methods, known as green routes, are increasingly recognized for their safety, lack of toxicity, and their potential to save both time and costs. These innovative green synthesis approaches involve various biological organisms such as microorganisms and plants, offering promising pathways to reduce metals through specific metabolic processes.

In our in vitro study, plant extracts from Eucalyptus camaldulensis was used as a reducing agent for silver nanoparticles, followed by their impregnation onto non-resorbable silk sutures. These AgNP coated silk sutures were later analysed using UV spectrometry and scanning electron microscopy. The antibacterial properties were tested by silver release test in petri-dishes, and their mechanical properties were assessed by the pull test to test its strength and surface profilometry to check for surface irregularity.

Materials and Methods

AgNP synthesis

The green synthesis of nanoparticles involved maceration of plant

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leaves to obtain the pure leaf extracts, followed by its lyophilization and then boiling the powder in distilled water until an aqueous solution is obtained. This aqueous plant extract was later reacted with silver nitrate to obtain a suspension which was then centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 30 min at 4°C.

The plant material utilized for the green synthesis of silver nanoparticles was derived from *Eucalyptus globulus*. The leaves were sourced in powdered form from the Nilgiris Hills in Kerala, India. Silver nitrate was obtained from Sigma Aldrich (Singapore) company. A leaf extract was prepared by combining 10 grams of powdered leaf material with 200 ml of distilled water at 85°C, followed by filtration through Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The resulting aqueous leaf extract had a concentration of 50 mg/ml. Distilled deionised water was used for solution. 16ml of (66mM) silver nitrate was mixed with 12 ml of aqueous leaf extracts from *eucalyptus globulus* mixed in deionised water for 30 minutes at 25°C. After reacting with silver nitrate solution, the phenols and flavonoid extracts from *Eucalyptus globulus* leaves developed a cloudy, muddy brown solution within 30 minutes at 25°C. This turbid brown suspension indicated the reduction of silver in the solution. The colloid suspension formed was later centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 30 min at 4°C. The silver nanoparticles were suspended in the suspension.

After centrifugation the suspension was subjected to UV spectrometry for confirmation of synthesis of nanoparticles.

AgNP impregnation into silk sutures

The silk sutures used in this study were acquired from Ethicon. They are black, braided, non-absorbable surgical silk sutures, size 3-0 (2 metric), and are catalogued under the code R 822. Produced by Johnson & Johnson Pvt Ltd in India, these sutures are recognized for their strength and dependability in surgical procedures

Once the presence of silver nanoparticles was confirmed in the suspension by the UV-spectrometry, multiple sets of 10 cm each length of silk sutures were cut and dipped into the suspension and kept undisturbed for a period of 5 days. 5 days later the silk sutures were picked one-by-one and then thoroughly rinsed with ionized water. Sutures were then dried at room temperature without sunlight. The rinsed and dried silk sutures were subjected to the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to confirm the presence of the silver nanoparticles impregnated in silk sutures.

Culture and sensitivity test of antimicrobial property

The AgNP coated silk sutures were placed into petri-dishes with agar gel and *Staphylococcus aureus* was used to check for antibiotic activity. *Staphylococcus* was selected due to its involvement in chronic multidrug resistant infections.

The AgNP impregnated sutures were inoculated into the agar plate for a period of 5 days. 5 days later *Staphylococcus aureus* bacterial culture was sprayed onto the agar plate and incubated for consecutive 5 days. The results obtained after 10 days was evaluated under microscopes by counting the colony forming units of bacterial growth. The same was performed with conventional silk sutures (without AgNP).

Mechanical profiling

The silver nanoparticles impregnated silk sutures were subjected to physical tests to compare changes in its properties to the original (non-coated) silk suture material.

Surface profilometry was carried out using a 3D non-contact

profilometer (ST400, NANOVEA, USA) to evaluate the surface texture of the materials. This advanced device enables accurate, contact-free three-dimensional mapping of surface topography, providing detailed information on texture and uniformity.

For assessment of physical properties, low-force fatigue testing was performed with a Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (DMA), specifically the ElectroForce 3310 model from TA Instruments, USA, under ambient temperature conditions. This apparatus applies precise, controlled forces to the silk threads to assess their fatigue resistance and overall durability. The principal parameter measured, T_{max}, indicates the maximum tension sustained by the silk threads during the testing process.

The T_{max} value is crucial for understanding the tensile strength and performance of the silk threads under cyclic stress, which is vital for evaluating their suitability for various applications. The application of these sophisticated instruments ensures a comprehensive evaluation of both the surface texture and mechanical properties of the materials.

Results

Biochemical results

UV spectrometry done on the suspension of the plant extracts to ascertain presence of silver nanoparticles, showed the peak of UV light absorption at a wavelength of 435 nm, that is in the visible light range, confirming the presence of AgNP evenly distributed in the suspension. When plant extract devoid of any AgNP was subjected to UV spectrometry, wavelength of UV light absorbance declined (figure 1). The aqueous suspension of plant extract was subjected to Transmission electron Microscopy (TEM) and the presence of AgNP in suspension was confirmed with particle sizes reaching up to 200nm (figure 2a). The AgNP impregnated silk sutures when also subjected to Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) to obtain pictures confirming the coating of AgNP. The AgNP was also found embedded into the matrix of silk sutures (Figure 2b).

Culture and sensitivity results

There was a significant reduction in the bacterial colonies on day 5 with 23 CU/ cm sq area in silver nanoparticles coated silk sutures inoculated plates when compared to the non-impregnated silk sutures with 78 CU/ cm sq area bacterial colony.

Figure 1: The UV spectrometry analysis

Figure 2: (a) The TEM image of suspension depicting the presence of nanoparticles; (b) The SEM image of the AgNP coated silk sutures

Physical test results

The AgNP impregnated silk sutures were subjected to pull test for tensile strength measurements, and the results obtained were comparable to non-AgNP impregnated sutures. There was a slight increase in % elongation at break in the AgNP incorporated sutures (table 1). The silk sutures coated (figure 3a) and uncoated (figure 3b) were also subjected to the surface profilometry test which revealed that the surface of both silk sutures was similar.

Discussion

Surgical site infections (SSIs) are a persistent concern in healthcare settings which leads to prolonged hospital stays, additional surgical interventions, increased healthcare costs, and even mortality in some cases. Despite advancements in surgical techniques, antimicrobial

prophylaxis, and infection control measures, SSIs continue to pose challenges for both patients and healthcare providers [6]. The risk of SSI is influenced by various factors related to both the patient and the procedure itself. Therefore, effective prevention strategies involve a comprehensive approach, addressing multiple risk factors simultaneously to minimize bacterial contamination and enhance the patient's immune response [7]. The use of the suture at surgical site for closure of incision line serves as a nidus for the infection which can lead to SSIs. The type of suture material, the design and properties of these suture materials, the duration of placements, all of these factors influence development of SSIs.

Thanks to advancements in technology, it's now feasible to integrate functional bioactive substances into sutures to augment their effectiveness. The advent of nanotechnology has enabled the synthesis of nanoparticles from traditional materials, endowing them with novel physical, chemical, biological, and biomedical characteristics [8]. Unlike conventional antibiotics, silver operates by adhering to the cell membrane of microorganisms and infiltrating them. Nanoparticles of silver tend to target the respiratory chain, disrupt cell division, and ultimately induce cell death in microorganisms. In our research, we've experimented with an innovative eco-friendly synthesis method to create silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) utilizing plant extracts. These extracts serve as reducing agents on metal surface, effectively shielding the newly formed silver nanoparticles from oxidation. In our research, we opted for eucalyptus leaves because of their distinct medicinal attributes, including antimicrobial and antifungal properties, as well as their abundance of antioxidants. Eucalyptus oils have also made a mark in healthcare, particularly in mouthwashes and health chewing gums, attributed to the presence of polyphenols [9].

Eucalyptus globulus belongs to the division Magnoliophyta, class Magnoliopsida, order Myrtales, family Myrtaceae, and genus Eucalyptus. Eucalyptus globulus is renowned for its therapeutic properties, making it a suitable candidate for nanoparticle synthesis. The choice of this specific plant was based on its rich phytochemical profile and its potential efficacy in facilitating green synthesis process. By using powdered leaves of Eucalyptus globulus, the study aimed

Figure 3: (a) The SEM image of the AgNP coated silk suture with presence of the nanoparticles coating the sutures; (b) The SEM picture of uncoated silk suture

Table 1: shows the results for tensile strength (pull test)

Material	Fmax (N)	Tmax (Mpa)	Elongation at break (%)
AgNP coated	11.2 ± 0.79	572 ± 90.14	13 ± 1.37
Non-coated	12.8 ± 0.46	648 ± 66.54	8 ± 0.84

to leverage the natural properties of the plant to produce silver nanoparticles in an environmentally friendly manner. The selection of *Eucalyptus globulus* reflects a targeted approach to harnessing the plant's intrinsic properties for nanoparticle synthesis, ensuring both the efficacy of the process and relevance of the plant material in the context of green chemistry practices.

The synthesis of silver nanoparticles proved to be a straightforward yet somewhat time-consuming process, primarily owing to the necessity of obtaining pure plant extract devoid of any impurities. The plant extracts were extracted directly from eucalyptus leaves following maceration, and the resulting extract powder underwent purification through lyophilization. This lyophilized eucalyptus leaf extract was then dissolved and reacted with silver nitrate to form a suspension. Through successive cycles of centrifugation, the suspension yielded a nanoparticle-containing solution. The surface plasmon resonance (SPR) of silver nanoparticles is significantly influenced by their size. Smaller nanoparticles, typically less than 20 nm, exhibit SPR peaks around 400 nm, while larger particles (50-100 nm) show shifts toward longer wavelengths, up to 500 nm. A reported SPR peak at 435 nm suggests that the nanoparticles are likely in the 50-70 nm size range, where pronounced peaks are common due to the interplay of size and electron confinement.

The silk sutures infused with silver underwent mechanical testing using pull tests, revealing that the silver-coated sutures exhibited lower tolerance to F_{max} compared to their non-coated counterparts. However, upon closer examination, it was found that the silver-coated sutures had a higher percentage of elongation. When observed under scanning electron microscopy (SEM) for surface profilometry, it was noted that the silver particles were embedded within the matrix of the silk sutures, preventing any unnecessary roughness or hardness in the suture material.

In this research, the synthesized silver nanoparticles consistently measured under 200 nm in diameter. The braided silk sutures, which feature fibre gaps exceeding 200 nm, presented an ideal matrix for these nanoparticles. Due to their smaller size relative to the fibre gaps, the nanoparticles were able to infiltrate and embed within the porous structure of the silk fibres. This successful incorporation was facilitated by the interaction between the nanoparticles and the silk matrix. The embedding of silver nanoparticles not only improves the antimicrobial properties of the sutures but also ensures their prolonged effectiveness. Consequently, these sutures are designated as silver nanoparticle-impregnated silk sutures, underscoring the significant achievement of integrating silver nanoparticles into the silk fibre matrix. This designation highlights the advanced nature and enhanced functional properties of the sutures resulting from nanoparticle impregnation.

The rise in percentage elongation while maintaining the surface profile suggests that the silver nanoparticles became integrated into the silk thread's matrix, thereby enhancing its strength.

In our study, we cultured nutrient agar plates with silver-coated silk sutures for 5 days before inoculating them with *S. aureus*. Following inoculation, the samples were then incubated for 5 consecutive days. The analysis revealed a threefold decrease in bacterial growth, as measured by colony-forming units (CFU), from 78 CFU/sq cm area for non-coated sutures to only 23 CFU/sq cm area for agar plates containing silver-impregnated silk sutures. The creation of these silver nanoparticles was conducted in the laboratory using readily available resources and with great simplicity, followed by their integration onto standard silk sutures. This process of synthesizing and applying silver onto the sutures has been termed

“green synthesis” due to the absence of harmful chemicals and the production of biodegradable by-products from the ensuing reactions. Silver nanoparticles contribute antibacterial and antimicrobial capabilities along with antioxidative properties, enhancing the patient's local immunity and effectively hindering the onset and dissemination of infections. By integrating silver nanoparticles into the silk suture matrix, bacterial adhesion is thwarted, and the formation of biofilm is inhibited due to the suture's enhanced antioxidant features. The application of silver nanoparticles onto conventional silk sutures has enhanced their characteristics, maintained their strength and surface smoothness while imbuing them with antimicrobial, antibacterial, and antioxidant properties. This modification introduces a new healing dynamic to wounds, reducing the risk of surgical site infections significantly.

Our study aimed to explore a different species of *Eucalyptus* tree leaves, known for their medicinal properties across various *Eucalyptus* genera. This choice was motivated by the potential therapeutic benefits these leaves could provide. Instead of employing Mersilk brand sutures, which are commonly used, we opted for braided silk sutures due to their cost-effectiveness. While braided silk sutures are frequently utilized in clinical settings for their durability and flexibility, they have not been extensively studied with respect to silver impregnation. Our research focused on evaluating the effectiveness of silver nanoparticle impregnation in these braided silk sutures, specifically assessing their antimicrobial efficacy and overall performance.

Conclusion

Creating silver nanoparticle-infused silk sutures is a straightforward and productive procedure, yielding superior sutures suitable for clinical application. These advanced sutures could potentially deter surgical site infections and minimize complications during wound healing. However, the assessment of these sutures' characteristics is limited to laboratory conditions, necessitating further clinical trials and animal testing to fully understand their performance in real-world surgical environment.

Ethics Committee Approval: The study was approved by Institutional Ethics Committee of Manipal College of Dental Sciences Mangalore, Protocol Reference number 22029.

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